

Exploration of Practice Teaching System Construction of Vocational Colleges under the Background of “1+X” Course-certificate Integration in China Taking Nanjing Polytechnic Institute as an Example

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Abstract. Practice teaching in vocational colleges of China is an important part to realize the course-certificate integration under the background of “1+X” certificate system. This paper analyzed the problems existing in the practice teaching section in the process of course-certificate integration from the aspects of present practice teaching system, training mode, teaching reforms, training base construction, and so on. This paper put forward the construction strategy of practice teaching system including enforcing school-enterprise cooperation to optimize the talent training program, reconstructing the practice teaching system, promoting the teaching reforms, and building the training base inside and outside the colleges. After practicing, the results showed that through the construction strategy, the practice teaching system became more reasonable, the quality of personnel training was constantly improved, and the triple-win among students, enterprises and schools was realized.

Keywords: “1+X” certificate system; course-certificate integration; practice teaching system; vocational colleges; construction strategy; exploration.

1. Introduction

In 2019, China issued the “National Vocational Education Reform Implementation Plan”, which requires piloting the “academic certificate + several vocational skill level certificates” (referred to as “1+X” certificates) system in vocational colleges and applied undergraduate colleges [1, 2]. By the end of 2024, 447 certificates have been released by the ministry of education of China. The implementation of the “1+X” certificate system puts forward new requirements for college students’ comprehensive ability, which means the practice assessment is the key and difficult part in the system while the traditional theoretical assessment is only the basis for the vocational college students.

Course-certificate integration is an important means and strong guarantee for the implementation of the “1+X” certificate system in vocational colleges [3, 4]. It realizes the connection of curriculum standards with the vocational qualification standards, and the same direction of teaching process and vocational skills training process, which promotes the further combination of the academic certificates and vocational skills level certificates. College students can obtain two certificates when they graduate from the colleges [5, 6].

In order to fully play the role of the “1+X” certificate system, the most critical factor is to promote the symbiosis of course and certificate, which means course-certificate integration has become the key to improve the college students’ professional ability and practical ability [3, 7, 8]. The construction of professional practice teaching system and the good integration of course and certificate based on the “1+X” certificate system is conducive to improving students’ comprehensive quality, optimizing the combination of educational resources and various economic factors, deepening the reforms of teachers, teaching materials and teaching methods (i.e. “three

education reforms”), and upgrading the teaching quality and the school-running pattern of vocational colleges [9, 10].

However, the practical ability is often the shortcoming of vocational college students due to the particularity of different majors. Therefore, how to deepen the reform of talent training mode and reconstruct the practice teaching system in order to realize the organic “1+X” course-certificate integration and thus comprehensively improve students’ practical ability is one of the urgent problems that should be solved for the vocational colleges at present in China.

2. Problems possibly existing in Practice Teaching Links

2.1 The supporting practice teaching system has not been formed

The goal of vocational education is to cultivate students’ professional ability and improve their post skills. The “X” vocational skill level certificate is an important index of the vocational students’ professional ability and post skills. However, most practice teaching in colleges still stays in the cognition practice or “herding-sheep” internship. Many practice assessment contents are only embedded in the theoretical assessment, and even the practice teaching especially for the certificate assessment has not been carried out. For instance, in 2019, there is no special practice teaching section for the skill level certificate for the students major in thermal energy engineering technology in Nanjing Polytechnic Institute. To some extent, the teaching system around the certificate training and assessment has not yet been formed, which seriously weakens the training effects and therefore violates the original goal of the “1+X” certificate system.

2.2 The training mode needs improving

Most manufacturing enterprises outside the campus implement strict post responsibility system, and many posts need to be certified. Take the students major in thermal energy engineering technology as an example, their ideal practice posts are in the power plants but they may not be allowed to carry out any operations during their internship because they often don’t have any vocational certificates and thus are not qualified. In the meanwhile, the teaching mode of most practice teaching links inside the campus is still dominated by teachers, and students cooperate to complete practicing or training tasks. The dominant position of students during the practice teaching is weakened, and the opportunities for students’ hands-on practice are also compressed. In short, the training on campus is far from the real post requirements of different manufacturing enterprises. Consequently, the practicing mode of vocational education needs to be improved urgently.

2.3 Practice teaching conditions are insufficient

The construction of practice teaching conditions is an essential requirement for the realization of course-certificate integration. However, for most majors in the vocational colleges, there always exists the problem of insufficient practice teaching conditions whether it is an on-campus internship base or an off-campus internship base combining work and study. The practice training conditions are limited compared to the increasing number of students, which then affect the goal of one-on-one practice. On the other hand, considering the particularity and singularity of the production and operation posts of enterprises, the training of vocational skill level certificates conducted by enterprises cannot carry out effective practice teaching activities entirely according to the training objectives from colleges, let alone carrying out targeted training according to the assessment requirements of vocational skill level certificates. Consequently, the training effects are often unsatisfactory.

2.4 Teachers often seem incapable of conducting the training

From the perspective of training teacher staff, the emergence of “X” certificates put forward higher requirements for the college teachers during their practice teaching guidance. In order to

achieve the real training objectives, it requires the training teachers should have a complete system of theoretical foundation and strong practical experience, and be capable of combining theoretical knowledge, practical operation and skill assessment. This exactly reflects the quality of the double-qualified teachers. However, at present, the full-time teachers in the vocational colleges are generally lack of the practical experience while the part-time teachers from the enterprises are often in great need of the teaching experience and there is no continuous teaching time during their guidance to the students. All these factors cause negative effects on the final realization of the certificate training objectives.

2.5 The development of practice teaching materials is still insufficient

Compared with the textbooks of theoretical courses, there are obvious deficiencies in the quantity and quality of practice training textbooks, and there are even fewer practice training textbooks especially for the “X” certificate assessment. For instance, as shown in Fig.1, in 2019, there are only 7 related teaching textbooks for the vocational skill level certificates in China, among which there is no supporting textbooks for the major of thermal energy engineering technology in our study. Although some colleges and social evaluation and assessment organizations have jointly compiled training manuals or handouts, most of them are still in the exploratory stage. As shown in Fig.1, 137 related textbooks have been published during the last six years, which reaches the peak value in 2021. But it is obviously insufficient compared to the released 447 certificates in China. Even worse, the targeted training contents, standards and measures for the “X” certificate assessment are not mature enough, and it is difficult to form an organic system with the whole professional talent training system.

Fig. 1. Amount of related textbooks of vocational skill level certificates published from 2019 to 2024 in China

3. Construction strategy of practice teaching system in the process of “1+X” course-certificate integration

The direct purpose of course-certificate integration is to cultivate compound and practical talents who are more in line with the needs of actual positions, and meet the professional needs of students’ learning and enterprises’ employment. Therefore, under the background of “1+X” certificate system, it lays more emphasis on the guidance of vocational qualification level certificates to the professional teaching during the realization of course-certificate integration. The construction of practice teaching system and the integration of “X” certificate standards should be based on social needs, and therefore school-enterprise cooperation is one of the most basic and effective construction strategies. As shown in Fig. 2, the assessment pilot units (vocational colleges or applied undergraduate universities) should strengthen the connection and cooperation with the manufacturing enterprises and social evaluation and assessment organizations, analyze the assessment contents and standards of vocational skill level certificates, and sort out the skill points

that candidates should study. Then, they should calibrate the talent training program, reconstruct the practice teaching system, set up the practice teaching links targetedly, and reasonably determine the class hours of the corresponding practice teaching links. Subsequently, according to the assessment site standards, they should improve the software and hardware conditions of the practice base, promote the reform of practice teaching methods, and strengthen the construction of professional teacher staff. Finally, in order to encourage candidates' enthusiasm to participate in the assessment, they should build or improve the credit bank. Only in this way, can both schools and enterprises, both teachers and students achieve the common improvement.

Fig. 2. Construction strategy of practice teaching system under the background of “1+X” course-certificate integration

3.1 Optimizing talent training program

A reasonable practice teaching system should be based on the accurate positioning of the talent training program. The implementation of the “1+X” certificate system puts forward new requirements for the training of professional talents. In this context, the important role of enterprises should be given full play. Colleges should actively cooperate with social evaluation and assessment organizations to accurately grasp the needs of the enterprises, analyze the core posts, professional abilities, post skills, and so on, and clarify the contents of the professional qualifications. Based on these, piloting colleges and universities revise the professional talent training program accordingly, integrating the vocational skill level assessment standards with the teaching standards, reforming the professional talent training program, which would lay a solid foundation for achieving the final goal of course-certificate integration

3.2 Reconstructing the practice teaching system

The practice teaching system is an important carrier to realize the training goal of “1+X” certificate system, which is the basis and key to ensure the quality of talent training. Therefore, vocational colleges must strengthen the connection with the enterprise and the certificate assessment and evaluation organization, inviting the enterprise experts participate in the construction of the practice teaching system, analyzing the professional ability requirements, clarifying the positioning of the curriculum systems, and building corresponding scientific practice teaching systems, especially the proportion of the practice teaching links, practice modules, practice contents, practice class hours, and so forth. In this way, the selection and determination of the teaching contents can fully cover all the operational skill points of the certificate assessment. As for the major of thermal energy engineering technology in Nanjing Polytechnic Institute, a two-week practice teaching section was built for the corresponding “X” skill level certificates.

3.3 Reorganizing the teaching contents of the practice teaching links

According to the ability goal required by the vocational skill level certificates, the skill assessment points of the certificates are connected with the practice teaching links after carrying out the vocational ability analysis, decomposing the vocational ability into typical work tasks, and then developing the corresponding practice teaching links and reasonably designing the practice training tasks. On this basis, the vocational ability training is subsequently integrated into the practice teaching links by optimizing the implementation plan of practice teaching, building high-quality curriculum resources and practice teaching resources. In the meantime, more scientific and reasonable assessment methods are designed and carried out to evaluate the college students' vocational skills and professional qualities by reforming and improving the assessment methods. That is integrating the process assessment, value-added and comprehensive evaluation methods into the assessment of practice links.

3.4 Promoting the “three education reforms”

The implementation of the “1+X” certificate system has facilitated vocational colleges to further promote “three education reforms” to meet the needs of professional talent training. It is required that vocational colleges should cultivate a double-qualified teaching team by organizing teachers to enterprises or assessment and evaluation organizations to strengthen their operational skills through various forms of trainings, such as on-the-job training in enterprises, visiting engineers and other governmental trainings. In this way, the practical skills, teaching level and organizational ability of the college teachers are comprehensively improved so as to make them become qualified evaluators and trainers. In the meanwhile, vocational colleges and universities should introduce experts and high-tech talents from enterprises and assessment and evaluation organizations to make up for the shortage of the amount and ability of teaching staff, and form a complementary team with college teachers. Consequently, a full-time and part-time teaching staff is finally created for the smooth implementation of the “1+X” certificate system.

Considering “1+X” certificate training is based on the real operating post, it is crucial for the vocational colleges to comprehensively promote the reform of practice teaching methods to strengthen the cultivation of students' professional ability and core literacy. That is rationally designing the practice teaching plan based on the combination of work and study, adopting the teaching mode of theory-practice integration, and implementing the task-driven and project-oriented teaching methods.

In order to meet the needs of the reconstruction of practice teaching contents, re-writing the teaching materials has become increasingly urgent. Focusing on the teaching needs and certificate assessment requirements, vocational colleges should develop three-dimensional and digital training materials, build high-quality practice teaching resources, and achieve online and offline teaching interoperability.

3.5 Co-constructing practice teaching base by school-enterprise cooperation

The construction of practice teaching bases inside and outside the college is the key foundation for completing the “X” certificate assessment. The construction of practice training bases should be carried out according to the construction standards of practice teaching conditions required by the social assessment and evaluation organization. Firstly, vocational colleges should sort out the existing software and equipment, and clarify the differences between training and assessment, then strengthen the construction of the training rooms on campus to make the hardware and software to meet the needs of teaching, training and assessing as much as possible. Secondly, vocational colleges dock school teaching process with the real manufacturing process by introducing hardware and software equipment in line with the new technology, new standards, and new norms from the enterprises. Last but not the least, vocational colleges should make full use of the teaching resource database, training equipment and software resources developed by the social assessment and

evaluation organizations, whereby colleges, enterprises and social assessment and evaluation organizations can make full use of their respective resource advantages and upgrade the construction of professional practice teaching bases [11]. In the long run, vocational colleges can break the barriers of the production-education integration, and gradually form a long-term cooperation mechanism of school-enterprise cooperation and mutual benefits [12].

4. Case study of Nanjing Polytechnic Institute

The teaching team in the major of thermal energy engineering technology in Nanjing Polytechnic Institute (NJPI) has actively carried out the teaching practice of course-certificate integration under the “1+X” certificate system since 2019, especially around the construction of the corresponding practice teaching system. After nearly 5-year exploration and practice, results prove that the implementation path (as shown in Fig. 3) according to the above construction strategy (as shown in Fig. 2) has strengthened the training students’ operational skills and deepened their understanding of the post; the students’ learning enthusiasm is motivated because obtaining the skill level certificates and credits synchronously, and the training effects are therefore enhanced.

Fig.3 Course-certificate integration frameworks for the major of thermal energy engineering technology

Through such standardized assessment, enterprises can directly test students’ professional skills and qualities, which lay a foundation for them to select qualified talents. The five-year exploring results that the assessment pass rate is over 90%(as shown in Fig.4). It should be noted that 2020 is the first year in which we conducted the assessment successfully. After 2020, we started the implementation strategy and path shown in Fig.2 and 3 with the help of social evaluation and assessment organization through school-enterprise cooperation and obviously great progress has been made since then.

Fig.4. Assessment pass rate during the last five years in NJPI in China

5. Conclusions

The construction of a scientific, standardized and rationale practice teaching system is an important part of building the teaching mode of course-certificate integration, and also one of the keys to the smooth implementation of the “1+X” certificate system. In the view of the problems existing in the practice teaching system under the background of current “1+X” certificate system, the main construction strategies of practice teaching system by school-enterprise cooperation are explored. Practice from Nanjing Polytechnic Institute shows that the proposed implementation path can effectively realize the “triple win” among students, colleges and enterprises.

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